

Artificial intelligence (AI) is advancing every day, and the results are extremely interesting. We can start to consider AI as a “helper” to propose solutions or support in the HiPEAC fields, i.e. for code generation or improving hardware. However, as the results are still of very variable quality, the results that AI proposes should be thoroughly verified before using them.

AI as helpers in the software and hardware domains

By MARC DURANTON, HARM MUNK and TULLIO VARDANEGA

Artificial intelligence (AI) covers an increasing number of application domains, and can be regarded as a revolution that may change the way we work. This also impacts core HiPEAC activities, in particular software development and hardware systems. We see AI systems helping the design of computers, including the routing of integrated circuits, or generating code from (textual or vocal) specifications. Large models, based on transformers (LLM, or large language models) have been diverted from their original purpose in language-to-language transformation (for example, translation of one language into another) to transforming specifications expressed in natural language into program code. Such transformers can explain code snippets and help debug them. However, as the results they provide at this stage can vary from being either correct or totally wrong, it is not advisable to use them directly in final products. The recommended use instead is to consider them only as helpers proposing options or solutions that need to be (manually) thoroughly verified for quality and conformity.

Key insights

- Large language models can be used to help software development, such as generating code from specifications expressed in natural language into code, or to explain code or help in debugging.
- As they can also propose solutions to complex optimization processes, they can be used in computer design, for example to prune design space exploration or to optimize the routing of integrated circuits (ICs).
- The quality of the results are still very variable, from fully accurate to totally erroneous, depending on the relation between the query and the prior learning undertaken by the model, so all results should be verified and validated before use. Therefore, for now they should be used only as “helpers”.
- The size of the problems that they can efficiently tackle is still small, so they should be used to generate software modules, for example, and not a full application, which embeds multiple disparate functionalities.

Key recommendations

- Europe should be present in this particular field of development, and investigate how AI can improve productivity in computer science and engineering, both for hardware and for software.
- Research on large language models is not very active in Europe (see the HiPEAC Vision article “Gigantic Transformers and megamodels: The next El Dorado for AI?”), but they are showing interesting results in the domain of software. Actions should focus on developing such models in Europe (including the computing resource for training and the collection of databases) so that European companies can benefit from the results.
- Currently, some results are impressive, but the general quality of their output is very variable. Hence, these AI models should be used only as “helpers” of human endeavours, suggesting solutions, and their results should not be used “as is”. Research on how to improve the overall quality of the results should be developed. Software engineering guidance should be expanded to ensure control and assurance over all products of AI-assisted software engineering tasks.
- Validation and verification of (automatically generated) code will become more and more critical. Methods and tools to test and validate code (vs. the specifications) should be a special focus. This will be even more important with AI helpers for coding.
- Europe should promote a foundational approach to AI for software-related initiatives aimed at establishing a quality-proven, inclusive, bias-free and explainable base of learnable code examples for use in future automated code-production workflows.
- AI can disrupt the electronic design and automation (EDA) market: newcomers to this field with resources in AI, such as Google, can propose (open-source) solutions that can change how EDA is structured today. Europe should be also a player in that field by investing in research and providing innovative solutions for the design of future hardware. This should be part of the European Chips Act.
- Use these AI tools in a supervised way to teach students to program.

Generating code: A side effect of language processing

Fully automated software production *per se* is neither advertised nor contemplated as one of the primary fronts for research and development in artificial intelligence. At the same time, however, those who operate in software development, professionals and practitioners alike, are witnessing evidence of very impressive results becoming available in what can be regarded as fully automated transformation of ideas (concepts, requirements) into deployable programming artefacts.

This area of development can be seen as a ramification of natural language processing (NLP) applications, where the input is human discourse, the middle point is the accurate interpretation of its semantics and mapping to a consolidated knowledge base, and the output is a software-artefact that meets the needs of the input and is obtained by machine learning. To some extent, the automatic coding workflow is simpler than general NLP, and more abundant with machine-readable “learnable examples”. In fact, general NLP operates on the total expanse of human discourse for syntax, semantics and format, which is a very large and complex problem space. Automated code production instead is limited to “programmable needs or wishes” for input, and benefits from vast riches of learnable examples in a multitude of online code repositories for a knowledge base.

However, these repositories should also come with a health warning. It is typical of the application side of engineering that, if something “can be done” by engineering means, the urge to do it, show it off, and leverage the immediate benefits of it (the tip of the iceberg, figuratively) tend to prevail over the more responsible and humanistic obligation to give that novelty solid foundation, as free of fundamental design and conception flaws as possible. At present we are witnessing the very same phenomenon with the most impressive advances seen in AI-powered software production [1] [2] [3].

Some problems of using large language models (LLM) for code generation

Currently, large language models still have considerable flaws:

- **Code quality:** Automatic code production is the result of coupling natural-language descriptions, mostly stemming from comments embedded in the code, to the code contained in large open-source code repository collections, such as GitHub and GitLab. However, due to their open-source nature, these repositories are not subject to any form of quality control. This entails the danger that the code produced by automatic coders may replicate the flaws from the existing code into new code.
- **Problem specification:** The correctness and completeness (in terms of solving the programming problem) of the code produced depends on the accuracy of the problem specification. If that specification is inaccurate, imprecise, or worse, incomplete, then the code produced may very well not be correct. It requires training to write good quality problem specifications, and it requires further training to be able to compare the specification and the produced code. Testing cannot offer much relief here, because the responsibility then shifts towards the ability to design test cases that cover all relevant aspects and required behaviour of the code. These new tools suffer from the subtle

but severe weakness of ill formulations of requirement specifications, and the lack of established and verified non-functional quality attributes in the current base of learnable code examples, as [4] cautions.

- **Limited size of the scope and databases for training:** Currently, AI tools such as ChatGPT can only generate code in the range of a page of code, outside of the range of complex real-world-style code of thousands of lines or more. The examples shown so far produce impressive results for small examples, producing code of a few hundreds of lines. However, how well such automatic coders perform when fed with large system specifications remains to be seen. The importance of the quality, and, above all, the completeness of the system specification grows very fast when proceeding to large systems. This is due to the nature of the training, where the AI tends to generate code in a similar size of the training samples. Therefore, they should be used in an incremental, hierarchical and modular way (e.g. the AI tool proposes the structure, which is checked by humans, then all blocks are individually tested and validated by humans). It is also very important to create more curated databases for the training of such models; for example, GitHub is not the best source for training those AI, as there are various severe deficiencies in the content of open GitHub code repositories [5].

- **Non-functional attributes:** We are witnessing a slow paradigm shift from correctness only towards code that must adhere to non-functional attributes as well, such as constraints on time (not just timing!), memory footprint, and, of fast-growing importance, energy consumption. No popular programming language of this moment is able to express such non-functional attributes (other than possibly in parameters that are taken into account when translating the program). Code repositories are thus equally lacking in the expression of these attributes, meaning that such attributes will also not be taken into account, even if the problem specification does express them.
- **Education:** There also appears to be a peculiar shift required in education, but that shift connects well with the observations above. In the past, students were given a problem statement and were required to implement the solution in a particular programming language for educational purposes. But what do we need future students to train for in the presence of these automatic coders? Certainly not in how to implement the solution. We need to train them in specifying the problem accurately by feeding them imprecise problem descriptions. But somehow they also need to be able to compare the output code with the problem description, and that requires training in implementation languages as well. This appears to be paradoxical.

Walkthrough of some examples

In 2020, GPT-3 [6] was the first very advertised large language model. According to Wikipedia [7], it *“is a standard transformer network (with a few engineering tweaks) with the unprecedented size of 2048-token-long context and 175 billion parameters (requiring 800 GB of storage). The training method is “generative pretraining”, meaning that it is trained to predict what the next token is. The model demonstrated strong few-shot learning on many text-based tasks. [...] Given an initial text as prompt, it will produce text that continues the prompt.”*

Some people experimented with GPT-3 to induce it to generate computer code. The results were surprisingly good, and a lot of

applications and start-ups proposed various solutions relying on this technology, as demonstrated in [8]. OpenAI (the creator of GPT-3) then developed another model in 2021, trained on code, called Codex [9]. Microsoft exclusively licensed the GPT-3 technology [10] from OpenAI, and used a distinct production version of Codex to power GitHub Copilot. *“GitHub Copilot uses the OpenAI Codex to suggest code and entire functions in real-time, right from your editor”* [11] and is available to programmers to improve their productivity; according to a survey carried out by GitHub [12], it seems to do this successfully. It is indeed true that high-level coding is becoming impossible with current languages and tools due to its increasing complexity. We will need better, forward-looking abstractions, tools and languages to gain a competitive advantage in software, because this trend will never reverse – it will only grow wider in application domains.

Competition between the major AI companies is also fierce in this area, due to the potential impact of this kind of application. As an example, in 2022 DeepMind (acquired by Google in 2014) published AlphaCode, an AI program capable of writing computer programs at a competitive level. AlphaCode achieved a ranking of top 54.3% in human competitive programming competitions with more than 5,000 participants [14].

In November 2022, OpenAI introduced ChatGPT [15] (“GPT 3.5”). This launch created significant hype on the internet and on social media because it was accessible to anyone [3] (contrary to the previous solutions which had more restrictive access,

although it should be noted that neither the source code and nor the weights of any of these models is accessible or in open source, to our knowledge).

Of course, there was a rush to test its code-generation and code-explanation capabilities. The results are quite amazing, especially the experiments done to “simulate” virtual machines, Python code and containers [16]. It can also explain code, and find bugs, as shown in the examples given by OpenAI. This can help significantly in improving programmer efficiency.

It should be noted that ChatGPT is not executing the code: it completes it from what it has learned. As with other large language models, the results generated by ChatGPT may also be incorrect, therefore all its results should be verified and checked. (Meta-AI uses the term “hallucinate” [17]: *“Language Models can Hallucinate. There are no guarantees for truthful or reliable output from language models, even large ones trained on high-quality data like Galactica. NEVER FOLLOW ADVICE FROM A LANGUAGE MODEL WITHOUT VERIFICATION”*). See the HiPEAC Vision article “Gigantic Transformers and megamodels: The next El Dorado for AI?” for further discussion of this topic.

The following example (carried out at the beginning of December 2022) shows some results of ChatGPT in term of code generation. Even if the model is not tuned for code generation, it can generate running code in several programming languages (Figure 2) and can write shell scripts (Figure 3).

OpenAI Codex

We’ve created an improved version of OpenAI Codex, our AI system that translates natural language to code, and we are releasing it through our API in private beta starting today. Codex is the model that powers [GitHub Copilot](#), which we built and launched in partnership with GitHub a month ago. Proficient in more than a dozen programming languages, Codex can now interpret simple commands in natural language and execute them on the user’s behalf—making it possible to build a natural language interface to existing applications. We are now inviting businesses and developers to build on top of OpenAI Codex through our API.

Figure 1: Introduction to OpenAI Codex explaining the genesis and some use of it, from [13]

AI AS HELPERS IN THE SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE DOMAINS

We tested the current limitations of the model using the programming language Forth, which is far less frequent on internet and code repositories, and has unconventional features. It is therefore unlikely that

ChatGPT is directly reconstituting what was in its training data set.

As seen in Figure 4, the code “execution” is correct, even if, as noted, it is not really

executed but “figured” by the tool from what it learned. It should be noted that what is shown in Figure 4 is not exactly correct: a Forth interpreter will give a prompt after the definition of the word “testGPT”, and it

Figure 2: Testing ChatGPT to generate a list of prime numbers in a few programming languages

Figure 3: Testing ChatGPT to generate a shell script

Figure 4: Testing ChatGPT to generate Forth code

Figure 5: wrong "execution" of Forth code by ChatGPT

is only when the user types “testGPT” that it is executed. A few days earlier, the model didn’t write the word before executing it, so we can guess that the model is evolving. It correctly guessed that the loop starts at “0” and should end at “16”. However, in the other example shown in Figure 5, the execution is wrong: on the left, it correctly guessed that the start is “5” but it stopped at “17” instead of “16”. The right side is also wrong: it correctly guessed that the 2 before “+loop” is the loop increment, but assumed that “17” is the number of iterations, and not the (exclusive) upper bound.

As seen in these very simple examples, the output in terms of programming help has major potential, but it needs constant inspection and verification of the results. So it is clear that these tools are not perfect but they can help to increase the productivity of a programmer if carefully used (i.e. if the verification is not taking more time than the creation of the code).

Another result of these experiments is that these tools can infer the results of code, without really executing it, which could be helpful if the execution of the real code takes a large amount of time and the verification of the results is easy (asymmetrical problem). For example, these systems can be used to generate a hypothesis or as a starting point for iterative simulations: instead of starting with random numbers and waiting for the algorithm to converge to the correct end point with a lot of iterations, the AI system can give a starting point near the final result, meaning that the number of iterations would be reduced and energy and time could be saved (always supposing that this will not be overtaken by the energy and time required by the AI model).

AI for hardware design and optimization

The capacity of AI to propose solutions without executing complex simulations can also be helpful to generate more efficient hardware. For example, Cadence Xcelium ML [18] is enhanced with machine learning technology, as are other aspects of chip design [19]: Synopsys’ DSO.ai solution is an artificial intelligence and reasoning engine capable of searching for optimisation targets in very large solution spaces

of chip design [20], while Siemens EDA (previously Mentor) also uses machine learning to accelerate the design process [21], as well as back-end wafer processing simulation, for example [22].

It is clear, therefore, that all the major established EDA companies already use AI to accelerate the chip-design process. However, newcomers in the EDA field are also appearing, such as Google which is already using machine learning to optimize the floor planning of their tensor processing unit (TPU) AI accelerators [23]. It should be noted that this result is available on GitHub [24], allowing others to improve the approach and possibly replace (part) of the EDA flow with these approaches in the future. Google wants to go further and use AI for architecting accelerators (as shown, for example, by its research tool PRIME [25] published in 2022). Chip manufacturers, such as NVIDIA with its PrefixRL [26] tool, are also in the race of using AI to build better chips. NVIDIA says that the “Hopper GPU architecture has nearly 13,000 instances of AI-designed circuits” [26].

Chip design uses languages such as VHDL and Verilog which are closely related to programming languages, so

large language models could also be used directly in the future to create new architectures. Research is already ongoing in this field [27].

It seems clear that AI techniques will be increasingly used to design hardware. AI has the potential to disrupt the EDA market: newcomers with AI resources, such as Google and NVIDIA, can propose (open-source) solutions that may change how EDA is structured today. Europe should also become a player in this field by commissioning research and providing innovative solutions for the design of the future hardware. This should be part of the European Chips Act.

Conclusion

While we are still at the dawn of the age of computer-generated program code, the clock is ticking at a maddening pace, so the advances are very rapid. Indeed, AI has shown great potential to make software development more productive by reducing the problem area, with indirect and equally large effects also in hardware design. The major incumbents in the AI field have a competitive advantage in this burgeoning area, and the technology discussed in this article has disruptive potential.

Figure 6: Result of Synopsys DSO.ai for optimizing design, from [28]

As we have noted, however, the results of large language models should always be rigorously checked, as they are not always correct and the reasons why they may not be correct are not immediately evident. One practical way to make this line of evolution more trustworthy and sustainable is to create quality code repositories on which large language models can be trained, and to further develop tools to help with (formal or not) verification and validation of code, wherever they come from, human or machine. Europe should be at the forefront of this initiative.

The European Chips Act is also an opportunity to build momentum in the field of AI-assisted hardware design. At the same time, the training of programmers will also have to be re-evaluated in light of these new tools.

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Figure 7: NVIDIA PrefixRL designs arithmetic circuits that are smaller and faster than circuits designed by a state-of-the-art EDA tool. (left) The circuit architectures; (right) the corresponding 64b adder circuit properties plots (from [26])

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Marc Duranton is a researcher in the research and technology department at CEA (French Atomic Energy Commission) and the coordinator of the HiPEAC Vision 2023.

Harm Munk is a senior systems and software architect and developer at TNO (QuTech).

Tullio Vardanega is an associate professor in the Department of Mathematics at the University of Padova, Italy.

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